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Louisiana species of the genus *Xestia* Hübner and the genus *Agnorisma* Lafontaine

Vernon Antoine Brou Jr. and Charlotte Dozar Brou
 74320 Jack Loyd Road
 Abita Springs, Louisiana, 70420
 E-mail: vabrou@bellsouth.net

Abstract. We address three species of the genus *Xestia* Hübner recorded for the state of Louisiana: *Xestia dilucida* (Morrison), *Xestia elimata* (Guenée) and *Xestia c-nigrum* (Linnaeus), and we also address new state capture records for *Agnorisma badinodis* (Grote) and *Agnorisma bollii* in Louisiana.

The medium-size brownish colored Noctuidae moth *Xestia dilucida* (Morrison) (**Fig. 1a**) is a commonly encountered fall species at the **Abita Entomological Study Site* (AESS), as is the slightly larger gray species *Xestia elimata* (Guenée) (**Fig. 1b**). The Louisiana parish records for these two species are illustrated in **Fig. 2**. Both species, have almost identical single-brood flight periods at the AESS, both populations peaking early to mid-November (**Figs. 3 & 4**).

Fig. 1. *Xestia* species, males: a. *X. dilucida*, b. *X. elimata*.

Fig. 2. Parish records for *X. dilucida* ● and *X. elimata* ★

Fig. 3. *X. dilucida* captured at sec.24T6SR12E, 4.2 mi. northeast of Abita Springs, Louisiana. n = 1,947

Fig. 4. *X. elimata* captured at sec.24T6SR12E, 4.2 mi. northeast of Abita Springs, Louisiana. n = 2,037

Lafontaine (1998) stated the range of both *X. elimata* (Guenée) and *X. dilucida* (Morrison) to include southern Maine to northern Florida and west to Eastern Texas, wild adults of *X. elimata* occurring August to September and *X. dilucida* occurring August to November. An adult *X. dilucida* is illustrated from Abita Springs, Louisiana in Lafontaine (1998). Neither species are pictured in Covell (1984), though both are mentioned under similar species to *Xestia badicollis* (Grt.). Lafontaine (1998) reported there are 52 species in the genus *Xestia* in America north of Mexico and about 200 species worldwide. This same author reported the range of *X. elimata* includes Vermont to east Texas.

Xestia c-nigrum (Fig. 5) is newly reported here for Louisiana from three parishes (Fig. 6) Iberville Parish, St. John the Baptist Parish and St. Tammany Parish.

Fig. 5. *Xestia c-nigrum* (Linnaeus, 1758) a. male b. female. Fig. 6. Parish records for *X. c-nigrum*.

Fig. 7. *Agnorisma badinodis* in Louisiana.

Fig. 8. Parish records for *Agnorisma badinodis*

Agnorisma badinodis (Grote) (Fig. 7) Type locality Maryland, [USA] is a species which occurs from southern Quebec and Ontario westward to North Dakota and southward to South Carolina, Mississippi and Texas (Lafontaine, 1998). The reporting of these five Louisiana parish records (Fig. 8) Caddo Parish, Claiborne Parish, Madison Parish, St. John the Baptist Parish and St. Tammany Parish are the first reports for this species occurring in Louisiana.

We recorded 29 males and two females of *A. badinodis* captured over the past 57 years involving continuous automatic-capture nightly light trapping. Lafontaine 1998 created a new genus name (*Agnorisma*) and placed three North American species into this genus, two of which we cover here. The third species *Agnorisma bugrai* (Koçak, 1983) is known from Nova Scotia to British Columbia in Canada and across the northern United States, but absent across the entire southern half of the United States from Florida to California except for Colorado and the eastern edge of Utah (Lafontaine, 1998).

Fig. 9. Wild adult *A. bollii* from Caddo Parish, Louisiana.

Fig. 10. Parish records for *A. bollii* in Louisiana.

Fig. 11. N.A. records for *A. bollii* illustrated in MONA.

Agnorisma bollii (Grote) (Figs. 9, 10, 11) is newly reported to occur in Louisiana. Type locality: Texas, USA. Lafontaine, 1998 states: "*A. bollii* occurs primarily west of the Appalachian Mountains from southern Ohio and southeastern Kansas southward to Mississippi and Arkansas", "East of the Appalachians it has been found in Maryland and the Chesapeake Bay area". "Adults have been collected between late September and early November" (Lafontaine, 1998). A single male specimen of *A. bollii* was captured November 4, 2018 in a UV light trap at Vivian, Caddo Parish, Louisiana (Fig. 9). The two Louisiana species of *Agnorisma* generally are easily separable with *A. badinodis* overall appearing chestnut brown in ground color, while *A. bollii* appears to have a dark gray ground color.

This study is a continuation of our 56-year Odyssey targeting the lepidoptera and other insects which occur in the state of Louisiana. Our half-century of publications include previously undocumented information e.g., new locality records, detailed phenology information based upon decades or more of actual wild captured adults presented in an easily understood format of 366-day phenograms, illustrations of the actual Louisiana captured adults and a review of current and past entomological literature.

*Abita Entomological Study Site (AESS): sec.24,T6S,R12E, 4.2 miles northeast of Abita Springs, St. Tammany Parish, Louisiana USA.

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